

PROPOSED EXECUTIVE ORDER NO. ____

MANDATING ALL ELECTIVE AND HIGH-RANKING PUBLIC OFFICIALS TO MAINTAIN, PUBLICIZE, AND NOTARIZE A LEDGER OF ALL CONTRACTS AND PUBLIC DOCUMENTS THEY SIGNED

Date Proposed: October 17, 2025

WHEREAS, transparency and accountability are foundational principles of good governance and essential to maintaining public trust in government institutions;

WHEREAS, elective officials and high-ranking officials exercise authority over public funds, contracts, and documents that significantly affect the welfare of the citizens;

WHEREAS, it is necessary to ensure that all government transactions and contracts are open to public scrutiny and that the identity of all signatories to such documents is verifiable and documented;

NOW, THEREFORE, I, _____, President of the Republic of the Philippines, by virtue of the powers vested in me by the Constitution and existing laws, do hereby order the following:

SECTION 1. Coverage. This Order shall apply to all elective officials and high-ranking public officials with a monthly salary grade or compensation exceeding Eighty Thousand Pesos (Php 80,000), including but not limited to:

- The President and Vice President of the Republic;
- Members of the Cabinet, Department Secretaries, and Undersecretaries;
- Senators and Members of the House of Representatives; and
- Governors and Mayors of provinces, cities, and municipalities.

SECTION 2. The Official Ledger of Signed Documents. Every covered official shall maintain, publicize, and notarize a Ledger of Contracts and Public Documents Signed (hereinafter referred to as the Ledger), to be updated and made public monthly.

The Ledger shall include the following details for each document or contract signed:

1. Title or Name of the Document or Contract;
2. Initials of All Other Signatories and the last four (4) digits of their plantilla number or birth number if private individual (e.g., Jonelle Peter Muñoz – JPM1234 or JPM12051990);
3. Amount Involved in the contract or document;
4. Notarization Details (e.g., Name of Lawyer, Date of Notarization and Notarial Register Entries such as Doc. No., Page No., Book No. and Series of ____); and
5. Brief Description of the purpose or scope of the document (e.g., “Construction of a four-storey public school building at [exact address]”). The description should be approximately 50 to 100 words.

SECTION 3. Publication Requirement. Each covered official shall publish their Ledger every month on their official government social media account or public website (e.g., official Facebook page), ensuring that the information is accessible to the public.

SECTION 4. Notarization and Record Retention. The Ledger shall be notarized at least once every quarter and may be stored or uploaded to an immutable digital platform for public record and verification.

All Ledgers and related documents shall be maintained for a minimum of ten (10) years, consistent with the document retention requirements of the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) to all taxpayers.

SECTION 5. Prioritization of High-Value Contracts. High Priority: All contracts and documents involving an amount exceeding Php 500,000 shall be promptly included in the Ledger.

Mandatory Disclosure: All contracts and documents involving an amount exceeding Php 5,000,000 are required to be recorded, published, and notarized in accordance with this Order.

SECTION 6. Independent Monitoring. Independent organizations, auditors, civil society groups, and qualified experts shall be allowed to review, verify, and audit the published Ledgers to promote transparency and detect possible misuse of public funds.

SECTION 7. Penalties and Automatic Suspension. Failure by any covered official to maintain, notarize, or publicize their Ledger in accordance with this Order shall result in automatic suspension from office, subject to administrative and legal proceedings under existing laws and regulations.

SECTION 8. Retroactive Compliance. Within three (3) years from the effectivity of this Order, all covered officials shall compile, notarize, and publicize all documents and contracts they have signed during their term of service.

SECTION 9. Local Ordinance. Local Government Units (LGUs) are required to adopt this measure through local ordinances to strengthen transparency and accountability at the municipal, city, and provincial levels.

SECTION 10. Effectivity. This Presidential Order shall take effect immediately upon issuance and shall remain in force unless amended, repealed, or superseded by law.

DONE, in the City of Manila, this ____ day of _____, in the Year of Our Lord Two Thousand and Twenty-Five.

BY THE PRESIDENT:

President of the Republic of the Philippines

PROPOSED BY:

JONELLE PETER C. MUÑOZ

Citizen of the Republic of the Philippines

Date Proposed: October 17, 2025

Submitted as a Citizen's Proposal under the Right to Petition the Government

(Article III, Section 4 of 1987 Constitution)

Proposed to **The Republic of the Philippines,**
through the Senate and House of Representatives